

2'-Carboxy Maleianilic Acid as Analytical Reagent for the Determination and Separation of Zr(IV) and Th(IV)

NEPAL SINGH and C. S. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad

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2'-carboxy maleianilic acid has been found to be a selective reagent for the estimation of zirconium and thorium and their separation from a binary mixture. The acid gives white crystalline precipitate at pH 4.5–7.0 of a composition $[\text{Zr}(\text{L})\text{O}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{L})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, at 130–140°. The ions Mg(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ni(II), Hg(II), Cu(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Pr(III), Bi(III), Sm(III), La(III), Cr(III), CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} and BO_3^{3-} do not interfere in the determination of zirconium and thorium.

ORGANIC acids and their derivatives have been investigated by several workers for the estimation of zirconium^{1–4} and thorium^{5–8}. The authors introduced 2'-carboxy maleianilic acid as a new gravimetric reagent for the determination of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) and their separation when present together by using a mixture of citrate and tartarate (1:1 molar ratio) as a masking agent for zirconium ion. Ammonium nitrate has been used for coagulation and for better crystallization.

Experimental

2'-carboxy maleianilic acid (m.p. 184°) has been prepared by condensing maleic anhydride with anthranilic acid⁹. The course of reaction is as follows:

Sodium salt of the acid was prepared by dissolving the required amount of the reagent in 0.1M NaOH solution and maintaining the pH by adding acetic acid.

Stock solution of zirconium and thorium was prepared from the requisite amount of $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Mercks) in distilled water. Metal content of the solutions were determined gravimetrically^{10,11}.

Determination of zirconium: Aliquots (containing 2.8–36.37 mg) of the standard solution of Zr(IV) were diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water, and heated about to 40–50° on a steam-bath, appropriate quantity of ammonium nitrate was added for better crystallization. The pH of the solution was adjusted at 5.5–6.8 by adding acetate buffer. 1%(w/v) solution of the reagent (CMAA) was then added with constant stirring. The white precipitate of the complex was digested on steam bath (60–70°) for about 30 minutes.

It was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4), washed with distilled water repeatedly, dried at 130–140° and weighed as $[\text{Zr}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_5)\text{O}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. The conversion factor from complex to metal is 0.2545. The precipitation is quantitative at the pH range 5.5–6.8.

The TGA curve indicates that the complex is stable upto 160° and completely oxidised to ZrO_2 at 600°. The complex is insoluble in common organic solvents. The average mean error and standard deviation are found -0.076 and ± 0.188 respectively. The results of estimations have been recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV) AS ANILIC ACID COMPLEX

S. No.	Weight of Zr(IV) taken (mg)	Weight of complex (mg)	Weight of Zr(IV) found (mg)	% Error
1.	9.12	35.88	9.13	+0.13
2.	13.68	53.56	13.63	-0.36
3.	18.24	71.47	18.19	-0.05
4.	27.25	107.2	27.28	+0.11
5.	36.37	142.6	36.29	-0.21

Determination of Th(IV): A known volume of the standard solution of Th(IV) (0.2M) was taken in a 400 ml beaker, diluted to 150 ml with distilled water and heated on a steam-bath at 40–50°. Appropriate amount of NH_4NO_3 was added and the pH of the solution was adjusted at 5.5–6.8 using acetate buffer. The solution of the reagent (1% w/v) was added with constant stirring. The white precipitate was digested on a steam-bath for about half an hour, it was allowed to cool and filtered through a sintered crucible (G-4). The complex washed with water, dried at 130–135°

and weighed as $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_8)(\text{OH})_3\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2$. The conversion factor from complex to metal is 0.2312.

The precipitation is quantitative at the pH range 5.5–6.8. The average mean error and standard deviation were calculated -0.096 and ± 0.178 respectively. TGA curve of the complex shows that it is stable upto 180° and decomposed to ThO_2 at 660°. The results are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Th(IV) AS COMPLEX

S. No.	Weight of Th(IV) taken (mg)	Weight of Complex (mg)	Weight of Th(IV) found (mg)	% Error
1.	9.21	20.28	9.095	-0.29
2.	18.24	40.58	18.20	-0.23
3.	27.55	61.30	27.50	-0.18
4.	33.06	73.72	33.07	+0.04
5.	82.65	184.60	82.80	+0.18

Effect of foreign ions : To study the influence of foreign ions on the determination of zirconium or thorium, a definite amount of Zr(IV) (13.68 mg/100 ml) and Th(IV) (18.24 mg/100 ml) was taken separately in 250 ml beaker and gently warmed. A known volume of the foreign ion solution (15-30 mg) was added prior to the addition of the reagent and the estimation was carried out according to the procedure adopted earlier. It was observed that Cu(II), Mg(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ni(II), Hg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Cr(III), Pr(III), Sm(III), La(III), Mn(III), Bi(III) do not interfere in the estimations at pH 5.5-6.8, because of

of tartarate and citrate (1:1 molar ratio) masks the Zr(IV).

Determination and separation of zirconium and thorium in their binary mixture : When Zr(IV) and Th(IV) ions are present together in a solution, thorium was precipitated first in presence of a mixture of citrate and tartrate, thereafter Zr(IV) ions were demasked from the filtrate by employing conc HNO_3 .

Procedure : The mixture containing known amounts of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) was taken in a 500 ml beaker, it was diluted to 150 ml with distilled water. Appropriate quantity of the masking agent (tartrate and citrate) and NH_4NO_3 was added. The solution was heated gently for 15 minutes and its pH was adjusted at 5.5–6.8 using acetate buffer. Aqueous solution of the reagent (1% w/v) was added (one fold excess) with constant stirring and thorium was determined as described earlier.

The filtrate containing Zr(IV) ions was concentrated to 25% of the total volume and then treated with appropriate quantity of conc HNO_3 and evaporated about to dryness. It was diluted with 100 ml of water and any adhere HNO_3 was just neutralised by sodium bicarbonate. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 5.5–6.8 using acetate buffer. The zirconium complex was precipitated and determined as described earlier. The results of the estimations are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The sensitivity of the organic acid is found 6.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 6.8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for zirconium and thorium ions respectively. The precipitate settles within an hour. The digestion at higher temperature does not affect the

TABLE 3—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV) AND Th(IV)

S. No.	Metal ions taken (mg)		Complex (mg)		Metal ions found (mg)		% Error	
	Zr	Th	Zr	Th	Zr	Th	Zr	Th
1.	9.12	11.02	35.8	24.52	9.13	10.99	+0.12	-0.27
2.	18.24	22.04	71.56	49.16	18.21	22.05	-0.16	+0.04
3.	22.80	44.08	89.40	98.20	22.75	44.05	-0.21	-0.06
4.	45.60	22.04	179.16	49.16	45.50	22.05	-0.08	+0.04
5.	13.68	33.06	53.52	73.72	13.62	33.07	-0.30	+0.03

their reluctance to form complex with the reagent. The ions such as CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} and BO_3^{3-} also do not interfere in the determination. The interference due to Ag(I), Tl(I), Fe(II) and Fe(III) can be avoided by adding a mixture of tartarate and edta (1:1 molar ratio). A mixture

of tartarate and citrate (1:1 molar ratio) masks the Zr(IV). The composition of the complex at 130–140° is constant, the analytical data presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3 indicate that 2'-carboxy maleianilic acid can be used as a promising gravimetric reagent. The precision is fair and the accuracy of the estimation is almost within permissible limits.

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